

From Symmetry to Stability: Quantifying Converter–Grid Impedance Asymmetry as Indicator of Stability Margin

Chirag Ramgopal Shah, *Graduate Student Member, IEEE*, Marta Molinas, *Fellow, IEEE*, Sjur Føyen, *Member, IEEE*, Roy Nilsen

Abstract—Although symmetricity in the converter controller is desirable for robust stability margins, a direct link between system-level asymmetricity and instability has yet to be clearly established. Converter control introduces three-phase asymmetricity through loops such as DC-link voltage control, a phase-locked loop, and a power synchronization loop. Furthermore, the inherently asymmetric topology of the two-level voltage-source converter, which converts a DC voltage into a three-phase balanced set, acts as the underlying origin of the asymmetricities that propagate into the control structure. Consequently, establishing a direct relationship between system asymmetricity (rather than control asymmetricity alone) and the stability margin is essential for understanding the underlying instability mechanisms. In this work, asymmetricity is quantified using the Asymmetricity Quantification Index (AQI), derived from the sequence-domain representation of the interconnected converter-grid impedance. Within this domain, symmetricity is identified through the definition of symmetrical matrices, which serve as the benchmark against which asymmetricity is measured. A robust and generalized analysis correlates AQI with the stability margin, including both grid-following and grid-forming control structures connected to the power grid. It is found that instability arises from increased asymmetricity in the combined converter-grid system, which is dominated by asymmetric control loops and operating points. Thus, reducing asymmetricity without compromising controller functionality can improve stability margins. The analysis is validated in both control-hardware-in-the-loop and power-hardware-in-the-loop environments.

Index Terms—Impedance, Small-signal Analysis, Power Converter, Symmetry, Asymmetry index.

I. INTRODUCTION

IMPEDANCE-BASED small-signal stability has gained significant attention in power electronic-dominated systems due to its practical applicability [1]. Therefore, understanding impedance characteristics is crucial for analyzing interactions between power converters and the grid. Recent industry guidelines, such as the UNIFI report, have begun linking specific impedance characteristics to converter behavior, for

example, associating high-frequency voltage-phasor stiffness with resistive-inductive behavior within $f_1 \pm 40$ Hz at the point of common coupling [2]. However, while such specifications describe desired impedance shapes, a rigorous understanding on how these characteristics fundamentally impact stability, irrespective on control objectives, remains an open question. This work addresses this question by providing generalized insights into the impedance structural characteristics and their direct link to the stability of the converter-grid, irrespective of the control structures employed.

Previous research has implicitly and qualitatively suggested that increasing controller symmetry enhances the stability of converter-grid systems. Asymmetricity in the controller arises from control loops such as a classical Phase Locked Loop (PLL), DC-link voltage control, and power controllers [3]. Several studies have demonstrated that mitigating this asymmetricity improves stability: eliminating the PLL and DC voltage controller asymmetricity enhances stability in weak grids [4], a symmetrical PLL design improves weak grid stability [5], and extending these principles to include power control loops further reinforces the trend [6]. Compensating for dq frame coupling introduced by AC voltage control and PLL has also been shown to improve stability [7]. Similarly, reducing sequence domain coupling in grid-forming converters enhances stability [8], and reducing DC voltage controller asymmetricity consistently improves overall system stability [9]. Adaptive suppression of frequency coupling has been proposed to extend stability improvements across a wider operating range [10]. Despite this body of work, two critical limitations persist: First, existing studies are largely confined to specific control structures, leaving the generality of the asymmetricity-stability relationship unverified. Second, there has been no clear quantitative metric for asymmetricity that enables a rigorous analysis linking instability to asymmetricity. This paper addresses this gap by establishing a direct, quantifiable link between the asymmetricity of the converter-grid system and its instability. The presented work introduces the Asymmetricity Quantification Index (AQI), derived from the sequence domain representation of the interconnected impedance, and demonstrates that this metric provides a generalized indicator of stability margins across both grid following and grid forming control structures. Analytical validation further substantiates the explicit relationship between system asymmetricity and instability.

The availability of a quantified asymmetricity metric enables

This manuscript has been submitted to the IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics on (09 April 2026) and has been rejected on (01 June 2026) on the grounds of lacking a theoretical framework to support the empirical observations.

Chirag Ramgopal Shah (Corresponding author), Sjur Føyen and Roy Nilsen are with the Department of Electric Energy at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway. (email: chirag.shah@ntnu.no, foyen.sjur@ntnu.no, roy.nilsen@ntnu.no)

Marta Molinas is with the Department of Engineering Cybernetics at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway. (email: marta.molinas@ntnu.no)

Fig. 1. (a) Grid Forming controlled converter-grid System. (b) Grid Following controlled converter-grid System. CC: PI-based Current Control with voltage feed-forward, VC: PI-based Voltage control, PLL: Conventional PI-based Phase Locked Loop, DVC: PI-based DC-link Voltage Control.

several novel analysis. By examining how the AQI varies with system stability margin, we directly observe how asymmetry evolves as stability increases or decreases. Parametric sweeps of asymmetric controller parameters under fixed grid conditions reveal a robust methodology for control parameter tuning based on asymmetry. Furthermore, the dependence of system asymmetry on the operating point provides critical insight into stability limitations: for a given set of control parameters, the converter's stable output range becomes evident through the lens of system asymmetry. Thus, analyzing the quantified asymmetry together with the stability margin yields fundamentally new understanding of converter-grid instability mechanisms.

In summary, the main contributions of this work are as follows.

- 1) A systematic asymmetry quantification of a three-phase converter-grid system is proposed, enabling a direct examination of the relationship between asymmetry and system stability margins.
- 2) The proposed Asymmetry Quantification Index (AQI) is analyzed for both grid-forming and grid-following control structures, demonstrating its general applicability.
- 3) A comprehensive analysis of the AQI with respect to different control parameters and operating conditions provides in-depth insight into the explicit link between controller-induced asymmetry and system stability margins.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section II describes the system under consideration and presents impedance modeling for both Grid forming and Grid following converters. In Section III, an impedance-based stability analysis is introduced and the quantification of system asymmetry via the AQI is proposed. Section IV, analyzes the asymmetry of the system in relation to the stability margin for two distinct control structures. Section V, provides experimental validation of the analysis using both hardware in the loop and power hardware in the loop environments. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

Fig. 2. Control Loops. (a) $P-f$ Droop. (b) $Q-V$ Droop. (c) DVC. (d) PLL. (e) Voltage Control (VC). (f) Current Control (CC).

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION AND IMPEDANCE MODELING

In this work, two types of converter control structures are considered. The LCL filter is used on the output of the converter terminal. The power grid is considered as an inductive grid with an ideal voltage source. Detailed description of both types of converter controls is given below with their impedance modeling and validation.

A. Grid Forming Control

The schematic of a GFM controlled converter connected to an inductive grid is shown in Fig. 1(a) with its control structure. The primary purpose of the presented GFM control structure is to provide voltage and frequency support to the grid. The $P-f$ droop loop generates an angle for the controller frame, whereas the $Q-V$ droop provides the reference voltage for the d -axis. When using a virtual resistor, the output of the virtual resistor loop is subtracted from the $Q-V$ droop output to generate a reference voltage for the voltage control loop. In the inner control, the cascaded voltage and current control loops are considered. The block diagram representations of the

$$Z_{inv} = \left(I - \left(G_{del} \left(G_{VC}^i G_A - G_{IC}^i G_B - G_{CC} G_{VC} K_{qv} G_{QC}^i \right) - G_{MC}^i \frac{V_{DC}}{2} \right) \right)^{-1} \left(I - \left(G_{del} \left(G_{VC}^v G_A - G_{IC}^v G_B - G_{CC} G_{VC} K_{qv} G_{QC}^v \right) - G_{MC}^v \frac{V_{DC}}{2} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3. GFM controlled converter impedance verification through single-tone frequency sweep.

individual control loops of the GFM control are shown in Fig. 2(a), Fig. 2(b), Fig. 2(e) and Fig. 2(f).

The GFM controlled converter impedance equation is derived analytically and provided in (1). The derivation steps are provided in the appendix B. The analytical model is verified with single-tone frequency sweep in the Control-hardware-in-the-loop (CHIL) environment. More information about the CHIL setup is provided in Section IV. As shown in Fig. 3, the analytical model matches very well with the measured impedance.

B. Grid Following Control

The schematic of a GFL controlled converter connected to an inductive grid is shown in Fig. 1(b) with its control structure. The primary purpose of the presented GFL control structure is to dispatch power in synchronization with the grid. The DC-link voltage is regulated by a PI-based controller. A classical phase-locked loop is used that aligns the capacitor voltage vector with the d -axis. PI-based current control with decoupling term and voltage feedforward is implemented in the current controller, similar to the GFM control. The block diagrams of DVC and PLL are shown in Fig. 2(c) and Fig. 2(d), respectively. The current control loop block diagram is the same as shown in Fig. 2(f).

The analytical impedance modeling of the GFL control is provided in [11] in the dq frame. In this work, validation of

Fig. 4. GFL controlled converter impedance verification through single-tone frequency sweep.

the analytical model is provided in the CHIL environment. As shown in Fig. 4, the analytical model derived in [11] matches very well with the measurement results.

III. IMPEDANCE-BASED STABILITY ANALYSIS AND ASYMMETRICITY QUANTIFICATION

In a simplified converter-grid system, the system can be subdivided into two parts at the point of common coupling. The converter-side circuit is referred to as a source, and the grid-side circuit is referred to as a load. In the case of GFL controlled converter, since converter control is providing current to the power grid without any voltage/frequency support, converter-side can be modeled as a current source or a Norton equivalent. In contrast, in the case of GFM controlled converter, the converter is providing voltage and frequency support, therefore the converter-side can be modeled as a voltage source or Thevenin equivalent. The grid is assumed ideal with inductive impedance; therefore, the grid is modeled as a Thevenin equivalent. For stability analysis, the assumption is that the converter is stable when the grid impedance is zero and the grid is stable without the converter [12]. It is important to recognize that the Norton and Thevenin equivalence representations constitute mutually complementary characteristics of the same linear electrical circuit. The selection of Norton/Thevenin equivalence is done from the perception about the circuit's behavior only. The

Fig. 5. Equivalent Circuit of a converter-grid System

simplified converter-grid circuit is shown in Fig. 5. The grid current is given by (2).

$$I_g(s) = (1 + Y_s(s)Z_g(s))^{-1} (I_s(s) - Y_s(s)V_g(s)) \quad (2)$$

Applying linear control theory to (2), it is determined that the system is stable when the eigen-loci of $Y_s(s)Z_g(s)$ (also called a return-ratio, L) do not encircle the point $(-1, 0)$ in the complex plane. The encirclement of eigen-loci is analyzed because the three-phase converter-grid system is a Multi-Input-Multi-Output system with a presence of frequency coupling due to asymmetrical control loop such as Droop control, DVC and PLL. If a balanced three-phase system is assumed (the zero sequence component is not excited), then the return-ratio can be described in a 2×2 matrix in the dq frame as given by (3).

$$L(s) = Y_s(s)Z_g(s)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} L_{dd}(s) & L_{dq}(s) \\ L_{qd}(s) & L_{qq}(s) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_s^{dd}(s) & Y_s^{dq}(s) \\ Y_s^{qd}(s) & Y_s^{qq}(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Z_g^{dd}(s) & Z_g^{dq}(s) \\ Z_g^{qd}(s) & Z_g^{qq}(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

A. Impedance Symmetry

The reason for analyzing the symmetry of the three-phase impedance is that the symmetrical system inherently provides a better control over the stability margin. However, the impedance of the converter introduces asymmetry due to controllers such as DC-link voltage control, a classical phase-locked loop, and power synchronization control. Therefore, the impact of asymmetry introduced by these control loops on the stability margin of the system is crucial to analyze the underlying instability mechanism. In order to analyze the asymmetry of the impedance, it has to be quantified first.

To understand the asymmetry of the three-phase impedance, consider a simple example of an arbitrarily symmetrical three-phase inductor with equal mutual coupling as shown in Fig. 6. In matrix form, the impedance is given by (4). Now, a symmetrical component transformation is applied to Z_L^{abc} to obtain its sequence domain equivalence [13]. The transformed impedance matrix in the sequence domain is given by (5).

$$Z_L^{abc}(s) = s \begin{bmatrix} L & M & M \\ M & L & M \\ M & M & L \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Here, ' s ' is a laplace operator.

$$Z_L^{0pn}(s) = S^{-1}Z_L^{abc}(s)S = s \begin{bmatrix} L + 2M & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & L - M & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & L - M \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where

$$S = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & a^{-1} & a^{-2} \\ 1 & a^{-2} & a^{-1} \end{bmatrix}, a = e^{j\frac{2\pi}{3}} \quad (6)$$

For this work, the assumption is made that the considered three-phase system is balanced. Therefore, the zero sequence component is ignored. The 2×2 sequence domain impedance is given by (7). An important aspect to observe here is that the off-diagonal elements are zero. If the three-phase inductors, shown in Fig. 6 are not symmetrical, then the off-diagonal in (7) will be non-zero.

$$Z_L^{pn} = s \begin{bmatrix} L - M & 0 \\ 0 & L - M \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

In the real closed-loop converter-grid system, the return-ratio matrix is observed for the stability analysis as discussed in the previous sub-section. Therefore, from a stability point of view, the system asymmetry is apparent when the return-ratio matrix is analyzed in the sequence domain. That means that if the system is a three-phase symmetrical, the off-diagonal elements in the sequence domain return-ratio matrix will be zero. In other words, if there is a presence of off-diagonal elements in the sequence domain, then the system is three-phase asymmetrical. The return-ratio matrix, $L^{pn}(s)$, in the sequence domain is obtained by performing a matrix operation as shown in (8) [3].

$$L^{pn}(s) = A_z L^{dq}(s) A_z^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} L^{pp}(s) & L^{pn}(s) \\ L^{np}(s) & L^{nn}(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where

$$A_z = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & j \\ 1 & -j \end{bmatrix}$$

The eigenloci of the sequence domain return-ratio matrix are given by (9). In the eigenloci equation, it is indicated that the last term $L^{pn}(s)L^{np}(s)$ is non-zero only when the system is three-phase asymmetrical. In other words, in the asymmetrical impedance case, eigenloci of the sequence domain return-ratio will differ from its diagonal element, whereas in the symmetrical case, eigenloci will be the same as diagonal elements of the sequence domain impedance.

Fig. 6. Symmetrical Three-phase Inductor

Fig. 7. Control-Hardware-in-the-Loop Setup. The plant model is implemented on CPU-1, and the controller model is implemented on CPU-2.

$$\lambda^{p,n}(s) = \frac{L^{pp}(s) + L^{nn}(s)}{2} \pm \sqrt{0.25(L^{pp}(s) - L^{nn}(s))^2 + \underbrace{L^{pn}(s)L^{np}(s)}_{\text{non-zero when asymmetrical}}} \quad (9)$$

Based on this observation, *Asymmetry Quantification Index (AQI)* is defined as the absolute value of the multiplication of off-diagonal elements.

$$AQI = |L^{pn}(s) \times L^{np}(s)| \quad (10)$$

When the system is three-phase symmetrical, then *AQI* will be zero. Any non-zero value of *AQI* at a given frequency indicates the measure of asymmetry. The significance of *AQI* can be obtained when it is observed in relation to the closed-loop stability margin of the converter-grid system. To explore this relation, two case studies, corresponding to two converter controls structures, are presented in the next section.

IV. CASE STUDIES

In this section, *AQI* of both GFM and GFL controlled converter-grid systems, shown in Fig. 1, are analyzed in relation to the system stability margin. The real-time simulator from OPAL-RT is used for the implementation of the circuit model. One of the CPU cores is used as a controller whereas the other CPU is used to emulate the plant model as shown in Fig. 7. There is no direct communication between these two CPUs internally. The measured signals are scaled down before being taken out through analog-out ports. These signals are looped back-in as analog-in, rescaled, and conditioned before being used in the controller. Therefore, the setup can be considered as control-hardware-in-the loop (CHIL) setup [14]. At first, instability is induced in the converter-grid system, and stability is analyzed utilizing corrected bode plots for the MIMO system [15]. *AQI* of both stable and unstable systems will be analyzed to observe the asymmetry of the system. Moreover, through the parametric sweep, the stability margin of the system is analyzed against the system *AQI*, which will clearly indicate the direction of the phase margin when the asymmetry of the increases/decreases.

A. Case Study 1: GFM controlled converter connected to power grid

The system and control parameters of the GFM controlled converter connected to the power grid are mentioned in the

Fig. 8. GFM validation results. a) Time-domain current in the dq frame. At $t=0.5$ s, virtual resistor is disabled. b) Single coordinate (corrected) bode plots without the virtual resistor, confirming the resonance frequency of 7 Hz in q axis. c) *AQI* at $f_{res}^q = 7$ Hz, indicating increase in asymmetry without the virtual resistor.

appendix A. In Fig. 8(a), the time domain waveform of the grid current is shown in the dq frame. With 5% frequency droop, at $t = 0.5$ s, when the virtual resistor is removed, an instability is observed with resonances growing in amplitude. The resonance frequency is 7 Hz in the dq frame. In 8(b), the corrected Bode plots [15] are shown without R_v . In the q axis, it is clearly observed that the converter and the grid impedance are equal in magnitude at 7 Hz with a phase difference of 180°. Therefore, the corrected bode plots confirm the marginal instability. For both stable and unstable cases, the *AQIs* are calculated at the corresponding resonance frequencies of the q -axis and shown in the table provided in Fig. 8(c). It is clearly evident that *AQI* of the converter-grid system increases when the virtual resistor loop is removed.

Now, it is more interesting to observe the trend in the phase margin with respect to the variation in *AQI*. To explore this, at first, frequency droop is varied. With variation in frequency droop, the potential resonance frequency of the q -axis also changes, consequently, the phase margin changes in the q axis. Please note that only the resonance frequency and the phase margin of the q axis is observed here because the system is more prone to fulfill the instability criteria in the q axis. In Fig. 9, it can be seen that, when the frequency droop increases from 2% to 5%, the resonance frequency varies slightly, but the phase margin reduces almost linearly, which eventually enters the unstable region just before 5% of the droop. The color indicates that when the phase margin is reduced, the

Fig. 9. Analyzing q - axis system asymmetry and stability margin with variation in frequency droop.

Fig. 10. Analyzing q - axis system asymmetry and stability margin with variation in virtual resistance.

system AQI also increases.

Similarly in Fig. 10, q - axis phase margin and AQI are analyzed with variation in virtual resistance. It was observed that without virtual resistance the system is unstable. The corresponding point in Fig. 10 is shown with a red point. When R_v gradually increases to 0.5Ω , the phase margin of the system increases significantly. With $R_v = 0.5 \Omega$, the stability phase margin of 12° is obtained. It is also observed that with an increase in the phase margin, the system AQI also decreases, indicating a more symmetrical system. Therefore, with the GFM controlled converter-grid system, it is evidently observed that phase margin and AQI are linked. When the phase margin is less, the system is more asymmetrical compared to the system with higher phase margin.

B. Case Study 2: GFL controlled converter connected to power grid

The system and control parameters of the GFL controlled converter connected to the power grid are mentioned in the appendix A. In Fig. 11(a), the time domain waveform of the grid current is shown in the dq frame. At $t = 0.5$ s, when the PLL bandwidth (f_{bw}^{PLL}) is increased to 75 Hz, an instability is observed with resonances growing in amplitude. The resonance frequency is ≈ 143 Hz in the dq frame. In 11(b), the corrected Bode plots are shown with $f_{bw}^{PLL} = 75$ Hz. In the q axis, it is clearly observed that the converter and the grid impedance are equal in magnitude at 143 Hz with a phase difference of 183° . Therefore, the corrected bode plots confirm the instability. For both stable and unstable cases, the AQI s are calculated at the corresponding resonance frequencies of the q - axis and shown in the table provided in Fig. 11(c).

Fig. 11. GFL validation results. a) Time-domain current in dq frame. At $t = 0.5$ s, the PLL bandwidth is increased to 75 Hz. b) Single coordinate (corrected) bode plots with PLL bandwidth of 75 Hz, confirming 143 Hz resonance frequency. c) AQI at f_{res}^q , indicating increase in asymmetry with higher PLL bandwidth.

It is clearly evident that AQI of the converter-grid system increases when the PLL bandwidth is increased.

In Fig. 12, the resonance frequency of the q - axis and the phase margin are analyzed relative to AQI when the PLL bandwidth is increased. It is clearly evident that when the PLL bandwidth is increased, the phase margin is decreased, which is in-line with current research work. However, more significantly, by observing the color of a line, it is evident that the AQI is also increasing when phase margin is moving toward the unstable region. The stable and unstable cases shown in Fig. 11(a) are highlighted with blue and red dots in Fig. 12, respectively.

The impedance of the converter also varies with the operating points. Therefore, the reference current I_d is changed with a PLL bandwidth of 75 Hz. The corresponding resonance frequency and the phase margin of q - axis is shown in Fig. 13. It is observed that the converter-grid system can achieve stability, having a small phase margin at lower current with a PLL bandwidth of 75 Hz; however, the phase margin goes into the unstable region as the current increases. Moreover, it is also observed that AQI increases when the phase margin moves from stable region to unstable region.

Analysis of both case studies has clearly shown and validated the relationship between the phase margin and the asymmetry of the system. When the phase margin decreases, the system asymmetry increases and eventually goes into the unstable range. In the next section, the analysis is expanded

Fig. 12. Analyzing symmetry and stability margin with variation in PLL Bandwidth.

Fig. 13. Analyzing symmetry and stability margin with variation in I_d current.

with experimental results and analysis.

V. EXPERIMENT VALIDATION

The experiments are carried out in the Norwegian Smart Grid Laboratory. The schematic of the experiment set-up is shown in Fig. 14. A constant DC source is assumed, which is emulated by the power amplifier. A two-level converter with an LC filter is used. The converter and power amplifiers are controlled by OPAL-RT OP5700. The Gate signals are generated by the field programmable gate array of the Zynq 7030 System on Chip, which is included in the local control board mounted on the converter. The local control board also performs signal conditioning and A/D measurements, which are transmitted to the OPAL-RT platform via fiber-optic cables. For the experiments presented, the control loops are implemented in OPAL-RT with a sampling time of $100 \mu\text{s}$.

For the converter control, current control with a classical PLL is used. Active damping based on voltage measurement [16] and voltage feedforward are also utilized in current control. The analytical modeling of this controller is verified with the impedance measurement through a single-tone frequency sweep. The results, shown in Fig. 15, show that the analytical model aligns very well with the measurement data.

The system and control parameters for the experimental case studies are provided in the appendix A. Under these parameters, when the current reference (I_{ref}^d) is increased from 5 A to 12 A, resonances are observed as shown in Fig. 16(a). The resonance frequency is 11.1 Hz in the dq frame. The corrected bode plots in Fig. 16(b) also show the potential resonance at 11.1 Hz. Now, when AQI is also observed for these two operating points as shown in Fig. 16(c), it is evident

1. DC source
2. Converter with LC filter
3. Transformer
4. Grid inductor
5. Controller in OPAL-RT
6. AC Source

Fig. 14. Experimental set-up at the Norwegian Smart Grid Laboratory. 2-level converter with LC filter is connected to the power grid, which is emulated by a power amplifier.

Fig. 15. Converter impedance verification through single-tone frequency sweep.

that the system has become more asymmetrical with 12 A of d - axis current.

Now, to validate the connection between asymmetry and the system stability, the resonance frequency and phase margin of the q axis are plotted with an increase in the reference current of the d axis in conjunction with AQI in Fig. 17. The plots clearly show that as the current of the d - axis increases,

Fig. 16. Experiment validation results. a) Time-domain current in dq frame. At $t = 0.5$ s, the d -axis current reference is changed from 5 A to 12 A. b) Single coordinate (corrected) bode plots with $I_{ref}^d = 12$ A confirms the resonance frequency of 11.1 Hz. c) AQI at f_{res}^q , indicating increase in asymmetry at higher current.

Fig. 17. Analyzing q -axis system asymmetry and stability margin with variation in frequency droop

the phase margin of the system gradually decreases and moves into the unstable region. Moreover, by observing the color of the line, it is also evident that the system asymmetry also increases gradually with a decrease in the stability margin. Therefore, the experimental case also validates the previously presented analysis.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, a systematic framework is developed to relate asymmetry in the converter-grid impedance to the stability margin of the overall system, building on the general premise that higher degrees of symmetry are typically associated with more stable dynamical behavior. Converter control inherently introduces asymmetry through elements such as the DC-link

voltage controller, the classical phase-locked loop, and power synchronization control. The resulting system-level asymmetry is quantified in the frequency domain through an Asymmetry Quantification Index (AQI). The AQI is analyzed for both grid-following and grid-forming controlled converter-grid system in relation to variations in system stability margins. The results consistently show that as the phase margin decreases, the AQI increases, indicating a progressive decrease in the system symmetry as the system approaches instability. For grid-forming control, increasing the $P-f$ droop or reducing virtual resistance values leads to a degradation of the phase margin under certain grid conditions, accompanied by a corresponding increase in asymmetry. Similarly, in grid-following configurations, reducing the PLL bandwidth and increasing the d -axis current result in lower phase margins and higher AQI values. Experimental validation further confirms this trend, demonstrating that increased converter output current leads to reduced phase margin and increased system asymmetry. Overall, the analysis establishes a clear and consistent link between converter-grid impedance asymmetry and reduced stability margins. It further highlights that improved stability is not solely a consequence of symmetric control structures, but rather of the symmetry of the combined converter-control-grid system as a whole. When such symmetry cannot be fully achieved in practice, the AQI provides a valuable guideline for tuning control parameters and defining safe operating regions to ensure stable converter-grid interaction.

APPENDIX A SYSTEM AND CONTROL PARAMETERS

TABLE I
SYSTEM AND CONTROL PARAMETERS ($f_g = 50$ Hz) - CHIL CASES

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
$V_{g,rms}^{ll}$	400 V	L_1, R_1	2 mH, 0.001 Ω
V_{dc}	700 V	C, R_d	50 μ F, 1 Ω
P_{rated}	20 kW	L_2, R_2	1 mH, 0.001 Ω
		L_g, R_g	4 mH, 0.01 Ω
GFL controller		GFM controller	
K_p^{CC}/K_i^{CC}	8.5/10000	K_p^{CC}/K_i^{CC}	8.5/10000
K_p^{DVC}/K_i^{DVC}	-0.38/-68.63	K_p^{VC}/K_i^{VC}	0.07/18.27
K_p^{PLL}/K_i^{PLL}	0.83/151	$Q-V$ droop	2%
ω_{VFF}	250 rad/s	$P-f$ droop	5%
		R_v	0.5 Ω

TABLE II
SYSTEM AND CONTROL PARAMETERS ($f_g = 50$ Hz) - EXPERIMENT CASE

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
$V_{g,ph}^{peak}$	50 V	L_1, R_1	0.75 mH, 0.065 Ω
V_{dc}	125 V	C, R_d	50 μ F, 0.3 Ω
P_{rated}	2.5 kW	L_g, R_g	1.5 mH, 0.03 Ω
K_p^{CC}/K_i^{CC}	0.94/40	K_p^{PLL}/K_i^{PLL}	1.52/70
K_{AD} (active damping)	0.07	ω_{AD}	100 rad/s
		ω_{VFF}	40 rad/s

APPENDIX B

DERIVATION OF GFM IMPEDANCE EQUATION GIVEN BY (1)

The capital letters I , V , and M denote steady state values of the current, voltage, and modulation index, respectively, while the small letters (i, v, m) denote current, voltage, and modulation index as variables. The entire frequency domain impedance modeling is performed in the synchronous reference frame dq . The subscript 's' denotes the system frame variables and the subscript 'c' denotes the control frame variables.

A. Inner cascaded control loop

The PI-based current control loop transfer function

$$G_{CC} = \begin{bmatrix} K_p^{CC} + K_i^{CC}/s & 0 \\ 0 & K_p^{CC} + K_i^{CC}/s \end{bmatrix}$$

The PI-based voltage control loop transfer function

$$G_{VC} = \begin{bmatrix} K_p^{VC} + K_i^{VC}/s & 0 \\ 0 & K_p^{VC} + K_i^{VC}/s \end{bmatrix}$$

The decoupling terms in both current and voltage control loops

$$G_{i,dec} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega_g L_1 \\ -\omega_g L_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, G_{v,dec} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \omega_g C \\ -\omega_g C & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The voltage-feedforward with low-pass filter

$$G_{VFF} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\omega_{VFF}}{s + \omega_{VFF}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\omega_{VFF}}{s + \omega_{VFF}} \end{bmatrix}$$

The filter inductor L_1 and virtual impedance

$$Z_{L1} = \begin{bmatrix} sL_1 & -\omega_g L_1 \\ \omega_g L_1 & sL_1 \end{bmatrix}, Z_{virt} = \begin{bmatrix} R_v & 0 \\ 0 & R_v \end{bmatrix}$$

Based on above defined transfer function, the converter output under the small-signal perturbation is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{m}^{d,c} \\ \hat{m}^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} \frac{V_{dc}}{2} &= G_{del} \left(G_{CC} \left(G_{VC} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_{L2}^{d,c} \\ \hat{v}_{L2}^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} - Z_{virt} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,c} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} \right) - (G_{VC} + G_{v,dec}) \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,c} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} \right) - (G_{CC} + G_{i,dec}) \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,c} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} \right. \\ &\left. + G_{VFF} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,c} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The '^' above variables indicate the small-signal deviation.

B. Active Power Loop

Active power is given by,

$$P = 1.5(v_{L2}^{d,s} v_C^{d,s} + i_{L2}^{q,s} v_C^{q,s})$$

Applying small-signal perturbation,

$$\hat{P} = 1.5 \left(\begin{bmatrix} I_{L2}^{d,s} & I_{L2}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} V_C^{d,s} & V_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L2}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L2}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \right)$$

with

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L2}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L2}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} sC & -\omega C \\ \omega C & sC \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Perturbed power can be written as,

$$\hat{P} = 1.5 \left(\begin{bmatrix} G_{PS}^d & G_{PS}^q \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} V_C^{d,s} & V_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (13)$$

where, $G_{PS}^d = I_{L2}^{d,s} - (V_C^{d,s} sC + V_C^{q,s} \omega C)$ and $G_{PS}^q = I_{L2}^{q,s} + (V_C^{d,s} sC - V_C^{q,s} \omega C)$.

The small-signal angle for the Clarke and Park transformation is given by ,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\theta} &= -\frac{1}{1 + T_f s} K_{pf} \hat{P} \\ &= \underbrace{\frac{-1.5 K_{pf}}{1 + T_f s}}_{G_{PS}} \left(\begin{bmatrix} G_{PS}^d & G_{PS}^q \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} V_C^{d,s} & V_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where, T_f is filter time constant and K_{pf} is a power-frequency droop co-efficient.

Under the small signal perturbation, the system frame to control frame voltage transformation is given by [17],

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,c} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} \approx \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} + V_C^{q,s} \hat{\theta} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} - V_C^{d,s} \hat{\theta} \end{bmatrix}$$

Substituting $\hat{\theta}$ from (14),

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,c} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} &\approx \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 + V_C^{q,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^d & V_C^{q,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^q \\ -V_C^{d,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^d & 1 - V_C^{d,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^q \end{bmatrix}}_{G_{VC}^v} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} V_C^{q,s} G_{PS} V_C^{d,s} & V_C^{q,s} G_{PS} V_C^{q,s} \\ -V_C^{d,s} G_{PS} V_C^{d,s} & -V_C^{d,s} G_{PS} V_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix}}_{G_{VC}^i} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Similarly, the current transformation is given by,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,c} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} \approx \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} + I_{L1}^{q,s} \hat{\theta} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} - I_{L1}^{d,s} \hat{\theta} \end{bmatrix}$$

Substituting $\hat{\theta}$ from (14),

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,c} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} &\approx \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} I_{L1}^{q,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^d & I_{L1}^{q,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^q \\ -I_{L1}^{d,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^d & -I_{L1}^{d,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^q \end{bmatrix}}_{G_{IC}^v} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 + I_{L1}^{q,s} G_{PS} V_C^{d,s} & I_{L1}^{q,s} G_{PS} V_C^{q,s} \\ -I_{L1}^{d,s} G_{PS} V_C^{d,s} & 1 - I_{L1}^{d,s} G_{PS} V_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix}}_{G_{IC}^i} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Also, the modulating signal transformation is given by,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{m}^{d,c} \\ \hat{m}^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} \approx \begin{bmatrix} \hat{m}^{d,s} + M^{q,s} \hat{\theta} \\ \hat{m}^{q,s} - M^{d,s} \hat{\theta} \end{bmatrix}$$

Substituting $\hat{\theta}$ from (14),

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{m}^{d,c} \\ \hat{m}^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} &\approx \begin{bmatrix} \hat{m}^{d,s} \\ \hat{m}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} M^{q,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^d & M^{q,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^q \\ -M^{d,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^d & -M^{d,s} G_{PS} G_{PS}^q \end{bmatrix}}_{G_{MC}^v} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} M^{q,s} G_{PS} V_C^{d,s} & M^{q,s} G_{PS} V_C^{q,s} \\ -M^{d,s} G_{PS} V_C^{d,s} & -M^{d,s} G_{PS} V_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix}}_{G_{MC}^i} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

C. Reactive Power Loop

Reactive power is given by,

$$Q = 1.5(i_{L2}^{d,s} v_C^{q,s} - i_{L2}^{q,s} v_C^{d,s}) \quad (18)$$

Perturbed reactive power is given by,

$$\hat{Q} = 1.5 \left(\begin{bmatrix} -I_{L2}^{q,s} & I_{L2}^{d,s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} V_C^{q,s} & -V_C^{d,s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L2}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L2}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (19)$$

Substituting i_{L2}^{dq} from (12),

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{Q} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = 1.5 \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} -I_{L1}^{q,s} - V_C^{q,s} sC + V_C^{d,s} \omega C & I_{L1}^{d,s} + V_C^{d,s} sC + V_C^{q,s} \omega C \end{bmatrix}}_{G_{QC}^v} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} + 1.5 \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} V_C^{q,s} & -V_C^{d,s} \end{bmatrix}}_{G_{QC}^i} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

the reference voltage is given by,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_{C,ref}^{d,c} \\ \hat{v}_{C,ref}^{q,c} \end{bmatrix} = -K_{qv} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{Q} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

where, K_{qv} is reactive power-voltage droop coefficient.

D. Impedance equation

Combining (11) with (15),(16),(17),(20) and (21),

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{m}^{d,s} \\ \hat{m}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \frac{V_{dc}}{2} = \left(G_{del}(G_{VC}^v G_A - G_{IC}^v G_B - G_{CC} G_{VC} K_{qv} G_{QC}^v) - G_{MC}^v \frac{V_{dc}}{2} \right) \begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} + \left(G_{del}(G_{VC}^i G_A - G_{IC}^i G_B - G_{CC} G_{VC} K_{qv} G_{QC}^i) - G_{MC}^i \frac{V_{dc}}{2} \right) \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

where,

$$G_A = (-G_{CC}(G_{VC} + G_{v,dec} - G_{VC} Z_{virt} Y_C) + G_{VFF})$$

$$G_B = G_{CC} + G_{i,dec} + G_{CC} G_{VC} Z_{virt}$$

The capacitor voltage under small-signal perturbation is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{m}^{d,s} \\ \hat{m}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \frac{V_{dc}}{2} - Z_{L1} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

Combining (22) with (23),

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_C^{d,s} \\ \hat{v}_C^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} = Z_{inv} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{i}_{L1}^{d,s} \\ \hat{i}_{L1}^{q,s} \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

where, Z_{inv} is shown in (1).

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Wu, F. Zhao, and X. Wang, "A Survey on Impedance-Based Dynamics Analysis Method for Inverter-Based Resources," *IEEE Power Electronics Magazine*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 43–51, Sep. 2023.
- [2] UNIFI Consortium, "UNIFI Specifications for Grid-forming Inverter-based Resources—Version 3," UNIFI, Tech. Rep. UNIFI-2026-2-1, January 2026.
- [3] A. Rygg, M. Molinas, C. Zhang, and X. Cai, "A Modified Sequence-Domain Impedance Definition and Its Equivalence to the dq-Domain Impedance Definition for the Stability Analysis of AC Power Electronic Systems," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 1383–1396, 2016.
- [4] X. Zhang, S. Fu, W. Chen, N. Zhao, G. Wang, and D. Xu, "A Symmetrical Control Method for Grid-Connected Converters to Suppress the Frequency Coupling Under Weak Grid Conditions," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 12, pp. 13 488–13 499, Dec. 2020.
- [5] D. Yang, X. Wang, F. Liu, K. Xin, Y. Liu, and F. Blaabjerg, "Symmetrical PLL for SISO Impedance Modeling and Enhanced Stability in Weak Grids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 1473–1483, Feb. 2020.
- [6] Y. Sun, X. Ruan, Y. He, Z. Lin, and Y. Yan, "Symmetrical Phase-Locked Loop and Power Control Loop for Grid-Connected Inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, pp. 1–10, 2025.
- [7] W. Wu, Z. Yang, S. He, H. Li, K. Zhang, and L. Ding, "Enhanced Operation of Grid-Following VSCs With Alternating-Voltage Control in Ultraweak Grids," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 2270–2284, Apr. 2025.
- [8] M. A. Elshenawy, A. A. A. Radwan, and Y. A.-R. I. Mohamed, "Analysis and Weakening of Sequence Impedance Coupling in Grid-Forming Converters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 3292–3304, Dec. 2024.
- [9] Z. Lin, H. Wang, M. Su, J. Lin, and Y. Sun, "Filtered Power-Based Frequency Coupling Suppression Control for Three-Phase Voltage-Source Converter Under Weak Grids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 4236–4247, Mar. 2026.
- [10] Z. Wang, H. Pan, P. Cheng, and L. Jia, "Adaptive Frequency Coupling Suppression Strategy for VSCs and Its Stability Region Analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 2442–2456, Jan. 2025.
- [11] Z. Yang, C. Shah, T. Chen, L. Yu, P. Joebges, and R. W. De Doncker, "Stability Investigation of Three-Phase Grid-Tied PV Inverter Systems Using Impedance Models," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2672–2684, Jun. 2022.
- [12] J. Sun, "Impedance-based stability criterion for grid-connected inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 26, no. 11, pp. 3075–3078, Nov. 2011.
- [13] G. Paap, "Symmetrical components in the time domain and their application to power network calculations," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 522–528, May 2000.
- [14] "IEEE Recommended Practice for Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) Simulation-Based Testing of Electric Power Apparatus and Controls," *IEEE Std 2004-2025*, pp. 1–146, Aug. 2025.
- [15] C. R. Shah, M. Molinas, S. Føyen, S. D'Arco, R. Nilsen, and M. Amin, "Single Coordinate Bode Plots for Stability Evaluation of MIMO Power Electronics Systems via a Frequency Coupling Corrective Factor," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 40, no. 8, pp. 10481–10495, Aug. 2025.
- [16] J. A. Suul, K. Ljokelsøy, T. Midtsund, and T. Undeland, "Synchronous Reference Frame Hysteresis Current Control for Grid Converter Applications," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 47, no. 5, pp. 2183–2194, Sep. 2011.
- [17] B. Wen, D. Boroyevich, R. Burgos, P. Mattavelli, and Z. Shen, "Analysis of D-Q Small-Signal Impedance of Grid-Tied Inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 675–687, 2016.